

This record provides an overview of the HEXA-X-II community on Zenodo, established in 2023. The community collects research outputs, reports, and other materials related to the HEXA-X-II project, which explores advanced wireless communication technologies and the evolution towards 6G. The purpose of this record is to offer a single, citable reference (via DOI) to the community as a whole. For detailed materials, please refer to the individual records included in the community.

Keywords: 6G, wireless communication, HEXA-X-II, research community, datasets, publications

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Category	Title	Identifier	Open access record name and link to record or document
Article in journal	3GPP-like Channel Models at Sub-Terahertz: Improved Cluster Generation and Experimental Verification	10.1109/TAP.2025.3564506	3GPP-like Channel Models at Sub-Terahertz: Improved Cluster Generation and Experimental Verification
Article in journal	5G Perspective of Connected Autonomous Vehicles: Current Landscape and Challenges Toward 6G	10.1109/MWC.014.2300277	5G Perspective of Connected Autonomous Vehicles: Current Landscape and Challenges Toward 6G
Article in journal	6G AI-Driven Air Interface — Hexa-X-II View	10.1109/MCOM.001.2400394	6G AI-Driven Air Interface — Hexa-X-II View
Article in journal	A Blockchain-based trust management collaborative system for transport multi-stakeholder scenarios	10.1364/JOCN.486503	Blockchain-based trust management collaborative system for transport multi-stakeholder scenarios
Article in journal	A SKG Security Challenge: Indoor SKG Under an On-The-Shoulder Eavesdropping Attack	10.1109/globecom54140.2023.10437629	A SKG Security Challenge: Indoor SKG Under an On-The-Shoulder Eavesdropping Attack - TechRxiv
Article in journal	Advancing Spectrum Anomaly Detection through Digital Twins	10.1109/MCOM.001.2400221	Advancing Spectrum Anomaly Detection through Digital Twins
Article in journal	Alamouti-Like Transmission Schemes in Distributed MIMO Networks	10.1109/lwc.2023.3308011	Alamouti-Like Transmission Schemes in Distributed MIMO Networks
Article in journal	Analyses of Beamspace MIMO Channels at 142GHz	10.1109/lawp.2023.3324614	Analyses of Beamspace MIMO Channels at 142GHz
Article in journal	Analysis of Oversampling in Uplink Massive MIMO-OFDM with Low-Resolution ADCs	10.1109/spawc53906.2023.10304436	Analysis of Oversampling in Uplink Massive MIMO-OFDM with Low-Resolution ADCs
Article in journal	Analysis of Uplink and Downlink Spatial Channel Reciprocity When Using Asymmetric Transceiver	10.1109/TVT.2024.3368093	Analysis of Uplink and Downlink Spatial Channel Reciprocity When Using Asymmetric Transceiver
Article in journal	Applying Digital Twins to Optical Networks with Cloud-Native SDN Controllers	10.1109/MCOM.003.2300105	Applying Digital Twins to Optical Networks with Cloud-Native SDN Controllers
Article in journal	Attention to Virtualization: Making Network Digital Twins Aware of Network Slicing	10.1109/MNET.2025.3552137	Attention to Virtualization: Making Network Digital Twins aware of Network Slicing
Article in journal	Beyond Diagonal RIS for Multi-Band Multi-Cell MIMO Networks: A Practical Frequency-Dependent Model and Performance Analysis	10.1109/TWC.2024.3499875	Beyond Diagonal RIS for Multi-Band Multi-Cell MIMO Networks: A Practical Frequency-Dependent Model and Performance Analysis
Article in journal	Beyond Multi-Access Edge Computing: Essentials to Realize a Mobile, Constrained Edge	10.1109/MCOM.017.2300056	Beyond Multi-access Edge Computing: Essentials to realize a Mobile, Constrained Edge
Article in journal	Combined DL-UL Distributed Beamforming Design for Cell-Free Massive MIMO	10.1109/LWC.2024.3383950	Combined DL-UL Distributed Beamforming Design for Cell-Free Massive MIMO
Article in journal	Configuring Transmission Thresholds in IIoT Alarm Scenarios for Energy-Efficient Event Reporting	10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3583867	Configuring Transmission Thresholds in IIoT Alarm Scenarios for Energy Efficient Event Reporting
Article in journal	Coordinated Jamming and Poisoning Attack Detection and Mitigation in Wireless Federated Learning Networks	10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3558672	Coordinated Jamming and Poisoning Attack Detection and Mitigation in Wireless Federated Learning Networks
Article in journal	Cross-Layer Integrated Sensing and Communication: A Joint Industrial and Academic Perspective	10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3595459	Cross-layer Integrated Sensing and Communication: A Joint Industrial and Academic Perspective
Article in journal	Deep Learning-Based Blind Multiple User Detection for Grant-Free SCMA and MUSA Systems	10.1109/tmlcn.2023.3283350	Deep Learning-Based Blind Multiple User Detection for Grant-Free SCMA and MUSA Systems
Article in journal	Defining Intent-Based Service Management Automation for 6G Multi-Stakeholders Scenarios	10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3554250	Defining Intent-Based Service Management Automation for 6G Multi-Stakeholders Scenarios
Article in journal	Delay Minimization for Rate-Splitting Multiple Access-Based Multi-Server MEC Offloading	10.1109/TNET.2023.3311131	Delay Minimization for Rate-Splitting Multiple Access-Based Multi-Server MEC Offloading
Article in journal	Demonstration of intent-based networking for end-to-end packet optical cloud-native SDN orchestration	10.1049/icp.2024.1803	Demonstration of Intent-Based Networking for End-to-End Packet Optical Cloud-native SDN Orchestration
Article in journal	Design Methodology for 6G End-to-End System: Hexa-X-II Perspective	10.1109/OJCOMS.2024.3398504	Design Methodology for 6G End-to-End System: Hexa-X-II Perspective
Article in journal	Detecting IP DDoS Attacks Using 3GPP Radio Protocols	10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3365425	Detecting IP DDoS Attacks using 3GPP Radio Protocols
Article in journal	Distributed MIMO Networks With Rotary ULAs for Indoor Scenarios Under Rician Fading	10.1109/OJCOMS.2024.3474170	[2406.19078] Distributed MIMO Networks with Rotary ULAs for Indoor Scenarios under Rician Fading
Article in journal	Enabling traffic forecasting with cloud-native SDN controller in transport networks	10.1016/j.comnet.2024.110565	Enabling traffic forecasting with cloud-native SDN controller in transport networks
Article in journal	Energy Beamforming for RF Wireless Power Transfer With Dynamic Metasurface Antennas	10.1109/LWC.2023.3343563	Energy Beamforming for RF Wireless Power Transfer With Dynamic Metasurface Antennas
Article in journal	Energy-Aware Federated Learning with Distributed User Sampling and Multichannel ALOHA	10.1109/LCOMM.2023.3312793	Energy-Aware Federated Learning with Distributed User Sampling and Multichannel ALOHA
Article in journal	Energy-Efficient Rate-Splitting Multiple Access: A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Framework	10.1109/OJCOMS.2023.3322047	Energy-Efficient Rate-Splitting Multiple Access: A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Framework
Article in journal	Energy-Sustainable IoT Connectivity: Vision, Technological Enablers, Challenges, and Future Directions	10.1109/ojcoms.2023.3323832	Energy-Sustainable IoT Connectivity: Vision, Technological Enablers, Challenges, and Future Directions
Article in journal	Energy-aware tinyML model selection on zero energy devices	10.1016/j.iot.2025.101488	Energy-aware tinyML model selection on zero energy devices
Article in journal	Ergodic Secrecy Rate Analysis and Optimal Power Allocation for Symbiotic Radio Networks	10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3301186	Ergodic Secrecy Rate Analysis and Optimal Power Allocation for Symbiotic Radio Networks
Article in journal	Evaluating the Beamforming Impact on Channel Dispersion Characterization Using Multiscenario Sub-THz Channel Measurements	10.1109/TAP.2024.3489959	Evaluating the Beamforming Impact on Channel Dispersion Characterization Using Multiscenario Sub-THz Channel Measurements
Article in journal	Evaluation of EMF Exposure From Distributed MIMO Antennas for 6G in an Industrial Indoor Environment	10.1109/TEMC.2024.3474038	EMF Exposure evaluation of Distributed MIMO - Ericsson
Article in journal	Exploiting Queue Information for Scalable Delay-Constrained Routing in Deterministic Networks	10.1109/TNSM.2024.3435769	Exploiting Queue Information for Scalable Delay-Constrained Routing in Deterministic Networks
Article in journal	Finite Blocklength Analysis for SWIPT-Enabled RSMA Networks Under Realistic Assumptions	10.1109/TWC.2025.3563963	Finite Blocklength Analysis for SWIPT-Enabled RSMA Networks Under Realistic Assumptions
Article in journal	Guarding 6G use cases: a deep dive into AI/ML threats in All-Senses meeting	10.1007/s12243-024-01031-7	Guarding 6G Use Cases: A Deep Dive into AI/ML Threats in All-Senses Meeting

Article in journal	IEEE 802.11az Indoor Positioning with mmWave	10.1109/MCOM.001.2300454	IEEE 802.11az Indoor Positioning with mmWave
Article in journal	In-band Ambient FSK Backscatter Communications Leveraging LTE Cell-Specific Reference Signals	10.1109/JRFID.2023.3280108	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10136397
Article in journal	Inferring Direction and Orientation From Polarized Signals: Feasibility and Bounds	10.1109/OJCOMS.2024.3462689	Inferring direction and orientation from dual polarized signals: feasibility and bounds
Article in journal	Integrated 6G TN and NTN Localization: Challenges, Opportunities, and Advancements	10.1109/MCOMSTD.2025.3569014	Integrated 6G TN and NTN Localization: Challenges, Opportunities, and Advancements
Article in journal	Introducing end-to-end location awareness in packet-optical networks	10.1049/icp.2023.1847	Introducing End-to-End Location Awareness in Packet-Optical Networks
Article in journal	Jamming Attack Mitigation in Wireless Federated Learning Networks Using Bayesian Games	10.1109/LNET.2024.3499360	Jamming Attack Mitigation in Wireless Federated Learning Networks Using Bayesian Games
Article in journal	Joint User Association and Resource Allocation for Hierarchical Federated Learning based on Games in Satisfaction Form	10.1109/OJCOMS.2023.3347354	Joint User Association and Resource Allocation for Hierarchical Federated Learning based on Games in Satisfaction Form
Article in journal	Malicious RIS Versus Massive MIMO: Securing Multiple Access Against RIS-Based Jamming Attacks	10.1109/lwc.2024.3355322	Malicious RIS Versus Massive MIMO: Securing Multiple Access Against RIS-Based Jamming Attacks
Article in journal	Merging Threat Modeling with Threat Hunting for Dynamic Cybersecurity Defense	10.1109/IOTM.001.2400061	Merging Threat Modeling with Threat Hunting for Dynamic Cybersecurity Defense
Article in journal	Minimizing Energy Consumption in MU-MIMO via Antenna Muting by Neural Networks with Asymmetric Loss	10.1109/TVT.2023.3339340	Minimizing Energy Consumption in MU-MIMO via Antenna Muting by Neural Networks with Asymmetric Loss
Article in journal	Minimum Collisions Assignment in Interdependent Networked Systems via Defective Colorings	10.52953/JNDY5511	Minimum collisions assignment in interdependent networked systems via defective colorings
Article in journal	Model-Based End-to-End Learning for Multi-Target Integrated Sensing and Communication Under Hardware Impairments	10.1109/TWC.2024.3522667	Model-Based End-to-End Learning for Multi-Target Integrated Sensing and Communication Under Hardware Impairments
Article in journal	Monostatic Sensing for Passive RIS Localization and Tracking	10.1109/LWC.2024.3367528	Monostatic Sensing for Passive RIS Localization and Tracking
Article in journal	Neyman Pearson Detector for Multiple Ambient Backscatter Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons using Near-Perfect Code	10.1109/JRFID.2025.3598152	Neyman-Pearson Detector for Ambient Backscatter Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons
Article in journal	OFDM-Based JCAS Under Attack: The Dual Threat of Spoofing and Jamming in WLAN Sensing	10.1109/JIOT.2025.3527062	OFDM-Based JCAS Under Attack: The Dual Threat of Spoofing and Jamming in WLAN Sensing
Article in journal	On Optimal MMSE Channel Estimation for One-Bit Quantized MIMO Systems	10.1109/TSP.2025.3531779	On Optimal MMSE Channel Estimation for One-Bit Quantized MIMO Systems
Article in journal	On the Ground and in the Sky: A Tutorial on Radio Localization in Ground-Air-Space Networks	10.1109/COMST.2024.3417336	On the Ground and in the Sky: A Tutorial on Radio Localization in Ground-Air-Space Networks
Article in journal	On the Spectral Efficiency of Movable and Rotary Antenna Arrays Under Rician Fading	10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3558304	On the Spectral Efficiency of Movable and Rotary Antenna Arrays Under Rician Fading
Article in journal	Performance Analysis of Active RIS-Assisted Downlink NOMA With Transmit Antenna Selection	10.1109/TVT.2025.3528379	Performance Analysis of Active RIS-Assisted Downlink NOMA With Transmit Antenna Selection
Article in journal	Performance Analysis of Passive/Active RIS Aided Wireless-Powered IoT Network With Nonlinear Energy Harvesting	10.1109/TWC.2024.3505296	Performance Analysis of Passive/Active RIS Aided Wireless-Powered IoT Network With Nonlinear Energy Harvesting
Article in journal	Phase Noise Resilient Neural Transceivers for High Data-rate sub-THz Links	10.1109/LWC.2024.3524722	Phase noise resilient neural transceivers for high data-rate sub-THz links
Article in journal	Physical Layer Deception With Non-Orthogonal Multiplexing	10.1109/TWC.2025.3535545	[2407.00750] Physical Layer Deception with Non-Orthogonal Multiplexing
Article in journal	Pilot-Aided Distributed Multi-Group Multicast Precoding Design for Cell-Free Massive MIMO	10.1109/TWC.2024.3361560	Pilot-Aided Distributed Multi-Group Multicast Precoding Design for Cell-Free Massive MIMO
Article in journal	Privacy Preservation in MIMO-OFDM Localization Systems: A Beamforming Approach	10.1109/LWC.2025.3560219	Privacy Preservation in MIMO-OFDM Localization Systems: A Beamforming Approach
Article in journal	RIS-Aided NLoS Monostatic Multi-Target Sensing under Angle-Doppler Coupling	10.1109/TVT.2025.3585281	RIS-Aided NLoS Monostatic Multi-Target Sensing under Angle-Doppler Coupling
Article in journal	RIS-Assisted Joint Differential Polarization and Phase Modulation for Non-Coherent Receivers	10.1109/LWC.2024.3496257	RIS-Assisted Joint Differential Polarization and Phase Modulation for Non-Coherent Receivers
Article in journal	Resilient-By-Design: A Resiliency Framework for Future Wireless Networks	10.48550/arXiv.2410.23203	Resilient-By-Design: A Resiliency Framework for Future Wireless Networks
Article in journal	Resource allocation and pricing for multi-server multi-model federated learning based on market equilibrium	10.1016/j.future.2025.108055	Resource allocation and pricing for multi-server multi-model federated learning based on market equilibrium
Article in journal	Sub-THz Communications: Perspective and Results from the Hexa-X-II Project	10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3591836	Sub-THz Communications: Perspective and Results from the Hexa-X-II Project
Article in journal	Sustainable 6G architecture: An organic evolution of 5G networks	10.1016/j.comnet.2025.111629	Sustainable 6G Architecture: An organic evolution of 5G networks
Article in journal	The Integrated Sensing and Communication Revolution for 6G: Vision, Techniques, and Applications	10.1109/JPROC.2024.3397609	The Integrated Sensing and Communication Revolution for 6G: Vision, Techniques, and Applications
Article in journal	Toward Interactive Multi-User Extended Reality Using Millimeter-Wave Networking	10.1109/MCOM.001.2300804	Toward Interactive Multi-User Extended Reality Using Millimeter-Wave Networking
Article in journal	Toward an Open, Intelligent, and End-to-End Architectural Framework for Network Slicing in 6G Communication Systems	10.1109/ojcoms.2023.3294445	[PDF] Toward an Open, Intelligent, and End-to-End Architectural Framework for Network Slicing in 6G Communication Systems Semantic Scholar
Article in journal	Traffic Learning and Proactive UAV Trajectory Planning for Data Uplink in Markovian IoT Models	10.1109/JIOT.2023.3339514	Traffic Learning and Proactive UAV Trajectory Planning for Data Uplink in Markovian IoT Models
Article in journal	Waveform Learning Under Phase Noise Impairment for Sub-THz Communications	10.1109/TCOMM.2024.3430982	Waveform Learning Under Phase Noise Impairment for Sub-THz Communications
Article in journal	Waveform Optimization and Beam Focusing for Near-Field Wireless Power Transfer With Dynamic Metasurface Antennas and Non-Linear Energy Harvesters	10.1109/TWC.2024.3503908	Waveform Optimization and Beam Focusing for Near-Field Wireless Power Transfer With Dynamic Metasurface Antennas and Non-Linear Energy Harvesters
Article in journal	Zero-Energy Devices for 6G: Technical Enablers at a Glance	10.1109/IOTM.001.2400138	Zero-Energy Devices for 6G: Technical Enablers at a Glance
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Integration of IP-Cores for the M ³ Architecture with Low Area Overhead: Accelerator Support Module	10.1109/ISOC62682.2024.10762360	Integration of IP-Cores for the M³ Architecture with Low Area Overhead: Accelerator Support Module
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	6G Function Modularity: Benefits, Challenges, and Options	10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10570793	6G Function Modularity: Benefits, Challenges, and Options
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A Cloud-Native Approach for Orchestrating 6G-Enabled Services at the Computing Continuum	10.1109/CAMAD62243.2024.10942907	A Cloud-Native Approach for Orchestrating 6G-Enabled Services at the Computing Continuum Semantic Scholar
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A Hybrid Method to Predict Network Traffic Demands for Each Link	10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807484	A Hybrid Method to Predict Network Traffic Demands for Each Link

Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A Modular COTS-Based High-Efficient Sub-THz Channel Sounder and Experimental Validations	10.23919/EuCAP60739.2024.10501693	A Modular COTS-based High-Efficient Sub-THz Channel Sounder and Experimental Validations
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A Reliable and Resilient Framework for Multi-UAV Mutual Localization	10.1109/VTC2023-Fall60731.2023.10333798	A Reliable and Resilient Framework for Multi-UAV Mutual Localization
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A Robust UAV-Based Approach for Power-Modulated Jammer Localization Using DoA	10.1109/VTC2024-Fall63153.2024.10757505	A Robust UAV-Based Approach for Power-Modulated Jammer Localization Using DoA
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A Secure and Robust Approach for Distance-Based Mutual Positioning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10571327	[2305.12021v3] A Secure and Robust Approach for Distance-Based Mutual Positioning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	AI-Driven Orchestration of 6G-Enabled Services Across the Computing Continuum	10.5281/zenodo.15790204	AI-Driven Orchestration of 6G-Enabled Services Across the Computing Continuum
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	AI-native architecture for 6G networks and services with model dependencies	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597080	AI-native architecture for 6G networks and services with model dependencies
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Accuracy-Latency Tradeoff in Approximate and Delayed Computing as a Game in Satisfaction Form	10.5281/zenodo.15046005	Accuracy-Latency Tradeoff in Approximate and Delayed Computing as a Game in Satisfaction Form
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	An East-Westbound Control Architecture for Multi-Segment Deterministic Networking	10.23919/IFIPNetworking62109.2024.10619797	An East-Westbound Control Architecture for Multi-Segment Deterministic Networking
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	An OpenAirInterface-Based Ambient Backscatter Communication System Using Pilots	10.1109/VTC2024-Spring62846.2024.10683474	PID2024002797.pdf
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	AoA-Based Physical Layer Authentication in Analog Arrays under Impersonation Attacks	10.1109/spawc60668.2024.10694672	AoA-Based Physical Layer Authentication in Analog Arrays under Impersonation Attacks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Applying Distributed Ledger Technologies for Trusted and Secure Network Topology Management in Multi-Stakeholder Environments: A Case Study from the ADRENALINE Testbed	10.1109/NoF62948.2024.10741509	Applying Distributed Ledger Technologies for Trusted and Secure Network Topology Management in Multi-Stakeholder Environments: A Case Study from the ADRENALINE Testbed
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Autonomous Single Antenna Receiver Localization and Tracking with RIS and EKF	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit58263.2023.10188365	Autonomous Single Antenna Receiver Localization and Tracking with RIS and EKF
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Backscatter, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces and MIMO Communications with a Multipurpose Antenna Array	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597094	Backscatter, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces and MIMO Communications with a Multipurpose Antenna Array
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Beam Management Manipulation with Adversarial Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	10.1109/GLOBECOM52923.2024.10900964	Beam Management Manipulation with Adversarial Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Beyond Diagonal Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces for Multi-Carrier RF Wireless Power Transfer	10.1109/WCNC61545.2025.10978386	Beyond Diagonal Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces for Multi-Carrier RF Wireless Power Transfer
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Building Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation from 2 to 260 GHz	10.23919/EuMC61614.2024.10732797	Building Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation from 2 to 260 GHz
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Channel Estimation in Low-Resolution Near-Field Massive MIMO Systems	10.1109/SAM60225.2024.10636448	Channel Estimation in Low-Resolution Near-Field Massive MIMO Systems
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Closed-Loop Automation in 6G for Minimum Downtime Task Continuity in Surveillance Cobots	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597048	Closed-Loop Automation in 6G for Minimum Downtime Task Continuity in Surveillance Cobots
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Comparison of Indoor Propagation Channels at 28 GHz and 140 GHz Bands	10.23919/EuCAP60739.2024.10500950	Comparison of Indoor Propagation Channels at 28 GHz and 140 GHz Bands
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Constellation Shaping Under Phase Noise Impairment for Sub-THz Communications	10.1109/ICC51166.2024.10622763	Constellation shaping under phase noise impairment for sub-THz communications
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Data-Aided Regularization of Direct-Estimate Combiner in Distributed MIMO Systems	10.1109/ICASSP49660.2025.10888738	Data-Aided Regularization of Direct Estimate Combiner in Distributed MIMO Systems
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Deceptive Jamming in WLAN Sensing	10.1109/RadarConf2458775.2024.10549000	Deceptive Jamming in WLAN Sensing
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Deep Learning-Based Pilotless Spatial Multiplexing	10.5281/zenodo.10678209	Deep Learning-Based Pilotless Spatial Multiplexing
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Deep Learning-based Joint Pilot and Data Power Control in Cell-Free Massive MIMO Networks	10.1109/VTC2024-Fall63153.2024.10757576	Deep Learning-based Joint Pilot and Data Power Control in Cell-Free Massive MIMO Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Multi-User RF Charging with Non-linear Energy Harvesters	10.1109/GLOBECOM52923.2024.10901606	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Multi-User RF Charging with Non-linear Energy Harvesters
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Demo: UE Assisted Ambient IoT in LTE Downlink, in real-time and open source	10.1145/3581791.3597285	Demo: UE Assisted Ambient IoT in LTE Downlink, in real-time and open source
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Demonstration of a Compositional Learning Framework for Open and Disaggregated Optical Network Control	10.1364/ofc.2024.m3z.10	Demonstration of a compositional learning framework for open and disaggregated optical network control - Archive ouverte HAL
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Discussion on 6G Architecture Evolution: Challenges and Emerging Technology Trends	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597056	Discussion on 6G architecture evolution: challenges and emerging technology trends
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Distributed Trust for Collaborative Network Management: Leveraging DLT in Multi-SDN Controller Environments	10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807463	Distributed Trust for Collaborative Network Management: Leveraging DLT in Multi-SDN Controller Environments
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Distributed User-Centric Cell-Free Massive MIMO with Architectural Constraints	10.1109/eucnc/6gsummit60053.2024.10597006	Distributed User-Centric Cell-Free Massive MIMO with Architectural Constraints.pdf
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Doubly 1-bit quantized massive MIMO	10.5281/zenodo.10606568	Doubly 1-Bit Quantized Massive MIMO
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Dynamic Drift-Adaptive Ensemble-Based Quality of Transmission Classification Framework in OTN	10.1109/ICTON59386.2023.10207229	Dynamic Drift-Adaptive Ensemble-based Quality of Transmission Classification Framework in OTN
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Dynamic Wideband Channel Sounding in an Urban Macrocellular Scenario at 15 GHz	10.23919/EuCAP63536.2025.10999363	Dynamic Wideband Channel Sounding in an Urban Macrocellular Scenario at 15 GHz
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	End-to-End Learning for Length-Invariant Radio Identification	10.1109/ANTS63515.2024.10898735	End-to-End Learning for Length-Invariant Radio Identification
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	End-to-End Waveform and Beamforming Optimization for RF Wireless Power Transfer	10.1109/SPAWC60668.2024.10694404	End-to-End Waveform and Beamforming Optimization for RF Wireless Power Transfer
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Enhanced data detection for massive MIMO with 1-bit ADCs	10.5281/zenodo.10606571	Enhanced Data Detection for Massive MIMO with 1-Bit ADCs
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Enhancing Sensing-Assisted Communications in Cluttered Indoor Environments through Background Subtraction	10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10571242	[2401.05763] Enhancing Sensing-Assisted Communications in Cluttered Indoor Environments through Background Subtraction
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Evaluating Fast and Grant-Free Uplink Access in Next-Generation Cellular IoT Networks	10.1109/6GNet63182.2024.10765754	Evaluating Fast and Grant-Free Uplink Access in Next-Generation Cellular IoT Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	FASIL: A Challenge-Based Framework for Secure and Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning	10.1109/csn64211.2024.10851771	FASIL: A challenge-based framework for secure and privacy-preserving federated learning
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Federated Learning for Anomaly Detection in Open RAN: Security Architecture Within a Digital Twin	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597083	Federated Learning for Anomaly Detection in Open RAN: Security Architecture Within a Digital Twin
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	FlexiPrint: Adaptive Radio Fingerprinting for Length Variability	10.1109/JCS64661.2025.10880647	FlexiPrint: Adaptive Radio Fingerprinting for Length Variability

Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Flexible Transceiver Platform for Holistic Radio Design Analysis	10.1109/6gnet63182.2024.10765785	Flexible Transceiver Platform for Holistic Radio Design Analysis
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Grouping intent-based packet-optical connectivity services	10.1049/icp.2023.2323	Grouping Intent-based Packet-Optical Connectivity Services
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Hybrid Receiver Design for Massive MIMO-OFDM with Low-Resolution ADCs and Oversampling	10.1109/WCNC61545.2025.10978435	Hybrid Receiver Design for Massive MIMO-OFDM with Low-Resolution ADCs and Oversampling
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Impact of Rough Building Material Surfaces on Reflection Coefficients from 5 GHz to 260 GHz	10.23919/EuCAP63536.2025.10999332	Impact of rough building material surfaces on reflection coefficients from 5 GHz to 260 GHz
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Indoor Backscattering Communication by Using Commercial LTE Pilots	10.1109/VTC2024-Spring62846.2024.10683260	Indoor Backscattering Communication by Using Commercial LTE Pilots - Aalto University's research portal
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Indoor Localization of Smartphones Thanks to Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons	10.23919/EuCAP60739.2024.10501308	Indoor Localization of Smartphones Thanks to Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Integrated Monostatic and Bistatic mmWave Sensing	10.1109/globecom54140.2023.10437391	Integrated Monostatic and Bistatic mmWave Sensing
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Integrating Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) into Indoor D-MIMO Networks for 6G	10.1109/vtc2024-fall63153.2024.10757793	Integrating Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) into Indoor D-MIMO Networks for 6G
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Intelligent Duty Cycling Management and Wake-up for Energy Harvesting IoT Networks with Correlated Activity	10.1109/IEEECONF60004.2024.10942799	Intelligent Duty Cycling Management for Energy-Aware Sustainable IoT Scenarios
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Intent-Based Network Resource Slicing in 6G	10.1109/NoF62948.2024.10741513	Intent-Based Network Resource Slicing in 6G
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	IntentLLM: An AI Chatbot to Create, Find, and Explain Slice Intents in TeraFlowSDN	10.1109/NetSoft60951.2024.10588917	IntentLLM: An AI Chatbot to Create, Find, and Explain Slice Intents in TeraFlowSDN
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Introspective Intrusion Detection System Through Explainable AI	10.1109/CSNet64211.2024.10851756	Introspective Intrusion Detection System Through Explainable AI
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Joint Communication and Sensing for 6G - A Cross-Layer Perspective	10.1109/JCS61227.2024.10646326	Joint Communication and Sensing for 6G - A Cross-Layer Perspective
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Joint Polarization and Spatial Modulation Using Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10570637	Joint Polarization and Spatial Modulation Using Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Label-Efficient Learning for Radio Frequency Fingerprint Identification	10.1109/WCNC61545.2025.10978444	Label-Efficient Learning for Radio Frequency Fingerprint Identification
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Malicious RIS Meets RSMA: Unveiling the Robustness of Rate Splitting to RIS-Induced Attacks	10.1109/GLOBECOM52923.2024.10901757	[2408.13035] Malicious RIS Meets RSMA: Unveiling the Robustness of Rate Splitting to RIS-Induced Attacks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation From 2 to 260 GHz and Extension of the ITU-R P.2040 Model at Frequency Above 100 GHz	10.1109/PIMRC59610.2024.10817451	Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation From 2 to 260 GHz and Extension of the ITU-R P.2040 Model at Frequency Above 100 GHz
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Model-Driven End-to-End Learning for Integrated Sensing and Communication	10.1109/ICC45041.2023.10278889	Model-Driven End-to-End Learning for Integrated Sensing and Communication
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Multi-Stakeholder Intent-based Service Management Automation for 6G Networks	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597032	Multi-Stakeholder Intent-based Service Management Automation for 6G Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Network Resource Allocation for Gaming Using MEC API and TeraFlowSDN	10.1109/NoF62948.2024.10741360	Network Resource Allocation for Gaming Using MEC API and TeraFlowSDN
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	New Access and Flexible Topologies in 6G: Architectural Implications	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597028	New Access and Flexible Topologies in 6G: Architectural Implications
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Neyman-Pearson Detector for Ambient Backscatter Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit63408.2025.11037131	Neyman-Pearson Detector for Ambient Backscatter Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Non-Orthogonal Multiplexing in the FBL Regime Enhances Physical Layer Security with Deception	10.1109/spawc53906.2023.10304549	Non-Orthogonal Multiplexing in the FBL Regime Enhances Physical Layer Security with Deception
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	On the Accuracy-Energy Tradeoff for Hierarchical Federated Learning via Satisfaction Equilibrium	10.1109/DCOSS-IoT58021.2023.00073	On the Accuracy-Energy Tradeoff for Hierarchical Federated Learning via Satisfaction Equilibrium
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	On the Radio Stripe Deployment for Indoor RF Wireless Power Transfer	10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10570703	On the Radio Stripe Deployment for Indoor RF Wireless Power Transfer
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	On the Spectral Efficiency of Indoor Wireless Networks With a Rotary Uniform Linear Array	2025 ISBN Information: ISSN Information: DOI: 10.1109/WCNC61545.2025.10978615	[2402.05583] On the Spectral Efficiency of Indoor Wireless Networks with a Rotary Uniform Linear Array
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Optimality of the Bussgang Linear MMSE Channel Estimator for MIMO Systems with 1-Bit ADCs	10.1109/SPAWC60668.2024.10694302	Optimality of the Bussgang Linear MMSE Channel Estimator for MIMO Systems with 1-Bit ADCs
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Optimizing 5G Network Availability: Comparison Between Reliability Block Diagrams and Markov Chains Approaches	ESREL-SRA-E2025-P5793	ESREL-SRA-E2025-P5793-cd.dvi
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Optimizing Queueing Delay Budgets in DetNets based on Strict Priority Queueing	10.1109/HPSR64165.2025.11038881	Optimizing Queueing Delay Budgets in DetNets based on Strict Priority Queueing
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Performance analysis of centralized and distributed massive MIMO for MTC	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit58263.2023.10188232	[2304.05451] Performance Analysis of Centralized and Distributed Massive MIMO for MTC
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Pilot-Based Uplink Power Control in Single-UE Massive MIMO Systems With 1-Bit ADCs	10.1109/CAMSAP58249.2023.10403514	Pilot-Based Uplink Power Control in Single-UE Massive MIMO Systems with 1-BIT ADCS
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Power and Rate Allocation for Energy-Efficient Rate-Splitting Multiple Access via Deep Q-Learning	10.1109/GCWkshps58843.2023.10465023	Power and Rate Allocation for Energy-Efficient Rate-Splitting Multiple Access via Deep Q-Learning
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Programmability for Flexible 6G Architecture	10.1109/FNWF63303.2024.11028720	Programmability for Flexible 6G Architecture
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Providing Anomalous Behaviour Profiling by extending SmartNIC Transceiver support in Packet-Optical Networks	10.5281/zenodo.15182931	Providing Anomalous Behaviour Profiling by extending SmartNIC Transceiver support in Packet-Optical Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	RIS-Aided NLoS Monostatic Sensing under Mobility and Angle-Doppler Coupling	10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10571183	RIS-Aided NLoS Monostatic Multi-Target Sensing under Angle-Doppler Coupling
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Reliable Angle Estimation in True-Time-Delay Systems with Real-Time Phase Calibration	10.1109/JCS64661.2025.10880636	Reliable Angle Estimation in True-Time-Delay Systems with Real-Time Phase Calibration.pdf
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Resource Allocation as a Market: A Case Study on Multi-Server Multi-Model Federated Learning	10.5281/zenodo.15046615	Resource Allocation as a Market: A Case Study on Multi-Server Multi-Model Federated Learning
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Revisiting Data Recovery Loops in 6G Networks	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597012	Revisiting Data Recovery Loops in 6G Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Robust Federated Learning for Wireless Networks: A Demonstration with Channel Estimation	10.1109/GLOBECOM52923.2024.10901627	A Robust UAV-Based Approach for Power-Modulated Jammer Localization Using DoA
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Secure AI/ML-Based Control in Intent-Based Management System	10.1109/CSR61664.2024.10679495	Secure AI/ML-based control in Intent-based Management System
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Security in Intent-Based Networking: Challenges and Solutions	10.5281/zenodo.10161420	https://zenodo.org/records/10161420

Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Security, Privacy, and Resilience Controls for the 6G End-to-End System Developed in Hexa-X-II	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit63408.2025.11036931	Security, Privacy, and Resilience Controls for the 6G End-to-End System Developed in Hexa-X-II
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Semi-Supervised End-to-End Learning for Integrated Sensing and Communications	10.1109/ICMLCN59089.2024.10624785	Semi-Supervised End-to-End Learning for Integrated Sensing and Communications
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Sub-THz Waveform Evaluation in the D-Band: A Proof of Concept Study	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597018	Sub-THz Waveform Evaluation in the D-Band: A Proof of Concept Study - OuluREPO
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Synergia: Device-Edge Server Association for ISAC-assisted Mobile Edge Computing Systems	10.1109/GLOBECOM52923.2024.10901178	Synergia: Device-Edge Server Association for ISAC-assisted Mobile Edge Computing Systems
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	The Role of AI Enablers in Overcoming Impairments in 6G Networks	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597102	The Role of AI Enablers in Overcoming Impairments in 6G Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	The Role of Oscillator Phase Noise in Maximizing Transceiver Energy Efficiency	10.1109/WCNC61545.2025.10978835	The Role of Oscillator Phase Noise in Maximizing Transceiver Energy Efficiency
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	The Use of Statistical Features for Low-Rate Denial of Service Attack Detection	10.1109/6GNet58894.2023.10317727	The use of statistical features for low-rate denial of service attack detection
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Towards Beyond Communication 6G Networks: Status and Challenges	10.1109/PIMRC59610.2024.10817395	[2501.04496] Towards Beyond Communications 6G Networks Status and Challenges
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Towards an AI/ML-driven SMO Framework in O-RAN: Scenarios, Solutions, and Challenges	10.1109/FNWF63303.2024.11028866	Towards an AI/ML-driven SMO Framework in O-RAN: Scenarios, Solutions, and Challenges
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Unsupervised Learning for Gain-Phase Impairment Calibration in ISAC Systems	10.1109/ICASSP49660.2025.10890700	Unsupervised Learning for Gain-Phase Impairment Calibration in ISAC Systems
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Uplink Power Control for Distributed Massive MIMO with 1-Bit ADCs	10.1109/GLOBECOM54140.2023.10437819	Uplink Power Control for Distributed Massive MIMO with 1-Bit ADCs
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Utilizing Causal Learning for Cognitive Management of 6G Networks	10.1109/ICMLCN59089.2024.10624867	Utilizing Causal Learning for Cognitive Management of 6G Networks
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	XcARet: XAI based Green Security Architecture for Resilient Open Radio Access Networks in 6G	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit58263.2023.10188316	XcARet: XAI based Green Security Architecture for Resilient Open Radio Access Networks in 6G
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Zero-Energy Devices for 6G: First Real-Time Indoor Localization Thanks to Ambient Backscattering of Commercial 4G UEs	10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit63408.2025.11037216	Zero-Energy Devices for 6G: First Real-Time Indoor Localization Thanks to Ambient Backscattering of Commercial 4G UEs
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Zero-Energy-Device for 6G: First Real-Time Backscatter Communication Thanks to the Detection of Pilots from an Ambient Commercial Cellular Network	10.1109/6gnet58894.2023.10317672	Zero-Energy-Device for 6G: First Real-Time Backscatter Communication thanks to the Detection of Pilots from an Ambient Commercial Cellular Network
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	waveSLAM: Empowering Accurate Indoor Mapping Using Off-the-Shelf Millimeter-wave Self-sensing	10.1109/vtc2023-fall60731.2023.10333840	waveSLAM: Empowering Accurate Indoor Mapping Using Off-the-Shelf Millimeter-wave Self-sensing
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	A New Framework for the Sum of Squared κ - μ RVs with Application to Sub-THz Systems	10.48550/arXiv.2508.06242	A New Framework for the Sum of Squared κ-μ RVs with Application to Sub-THz Systems
Chapters in books	Addressing Privacy Concerns in Joint Communication and Sensing for 6G Networks: Challenges and Prospects	10.1007/978-3-031-68024-3_5	Addressing Privacy Concerns in Joint Communication and Sensing for 6G Networks: Challenges and Prospects
Preprint	6G RIS-aided Single-LEO Localization with Slow and Fast Doppler Effects	10.48550/arXiv.2410.11010	6G RIS-aided Single-LEO Localization with Slow and Fast Doppler Effects
Preprint	BER Prediction of Distributed MISO Systems using Beamsteering with Phase Compensation in mmWave Channels	10.5281/zenodo.15296803	BER Prediction of Distributed MISO Systems using Beamsteering with Phase Compensation in mmWave Channels
Preprint	Demonstrating Interoperable Channel State Feedback Compression with Machine Learning	10.48550/arXiv.2506.21796	[2506.21796] Demonstrating Interoperable Channel State Feedback Compression with Machine Learning
Preprint	First Real-Time Detection of Ambient Backscatters using Uplink Sounding Reference Signals of a Commercial 4G Smartphone	10.48550/arXiv.2501.15576	[2501.15576v2] First Real-Time Detection of Ambient Backscatters using Uplink Sounding Reference Signals of a Commercial 4G Smartphone
Preprint	Goal-Oriented Sensor Reporting Scheduling for Non-linear Dynamic System Monitoring	10.48550/arXiv.2405.20983	Goal-Oriented Sensor Reporting Scheduling for Non-linear Dynamic System Monitoring
Preprint	Leaky Wave Antenna-Equipped RF Chipless Tags for Orientation Estimation	10.48550/arXiv.2409.00501	Leaky Wave Antenna-Equipped RF Chipless Tags for Orientation Estimation
Preprint	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces-Assisted Integrated Access and Backhaul	10.48550/arXiv.2502.12011	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces-Assisted Integrated Access and Backhaul
Preprint	Reduction of Wideband Phase Noise in 6G Radio Links Utilizing Multiple Subarrays with Shared but Delayed Local Oscillator Signals	10.36227/techrxiv.175339355.54411475/v1	Reduction of Wideband Phase Noise in 6G Radio Links Utilizing Multiple Subarrays with Shared but Delayed Local Oscillator Signals - TechRxiv
Preprint	Wireless Energy Transfer Beamforming Optimization for Intelligent Transmitting Surface	10.48550/arXiv.2507.06805	Wireless Energy Transfer Beamforming Optimization for Intelligent Transmitting Surface
Other	6G KPIs - Definitions and Target Values	10.5281/zenodo.14621168	6G KPIs - Definitions and Target Values
Other	6G series workshop by Hexa-X-II 2025: Hexa-X-II Architecture enabler design	10.5281/zenodo.15516556	6G series workshop by Hexa-X-II 2025: Hexa-X-II Architecture enabler design
Other	Demo: Ambient Backscatter Communication with Convolutional Code based on LTE Pilots	10.5281/zenodo.15642846	Demo: Ambient Backscatter Communication with Convolutional Code based on LTE Pilots
Other	Dynamically Fine-Tuned Neural Compressor for FDD Massive MIMO CSI Feedback	10.5281/zenodo.15995566	Dynamically Fine-Tuned Neural Compressor for FDD Massive MIMO CSI Feedback
Other	European 6G vision from fundamental research to standardization	10.5281/zenodo.15672940	European 6G vision from fundamental research to standardization
Other	Hexa-X Laying the Foundation for 6G and Hexa-X-II Paving the Road to 6G Systemization	https://www.comsoc.org/publications/ctn/looking-back-our-predictions-and-looking-ahead-future	Looking Back to Our Predictions and Looking Ahead to the Future
Other	Hexa-X-II NTN view for ETSI NTN workshop in Sophia-Antipolis	10.5281/zenodo.15729804	Hexa-X-II NTN view for ETSI NTN workshop in Sophia-Antipolis
Other	Hexa-X-II: 6G architectural framework and enablers	10.5281/zenodo.15753468	Hexa-X-II: 6G architectural framework and enablers
Other	Hexa-X-II: Draft foundation for 6G system design	10.5281/zenodo.15005893	Hexa-X-II: Draft foundation for 6G system design
Other	High-Power and Safe RF Wireless Charging: Cautious Deployment and Operation	10.1109/MWC.017.2300462	High-Power and Safe RF Wireless Charging: Cautious Deployment and Operation
Other	Introduction to Hexa-X-II	10.5281/zenodo.15005797	Introduction to Hexa-X-II
Other	Positioning-Aided Channel Estimation for Multi-LEO Satellite Cooperative Communications	10.48550/arxiv.2502.05808	Positioning-Aided Channel Estimation for Multi-LEO Satellite Cooperative Communications
Other	Sense-then-Charge: Wireless Power Transfer to Unresponsive Devices with Unknown Location	10.48550/arXiv.2504.20580	Sense-then-Charge: Wireless Power Transfer to Unresponsive Devices with Unknown Location
Other	Update from Hexa-X-II and global alignment	10.5281/zenodo.15673032	Update from Hexa-X-II and global alignment

Other	Welcome and update from the organizing project Hexa-X-II	10.5281/zenodo.15006090	Welcome and update from the organizing project Hexa-X-II
Other	White paper: AI/ML as a Key Enabler of 6G Networks: Methodology, Approach and AI-Mechanisms in SNS JU	10.5281/zenodo.14623109	AI/ML as a Key Enabler of 6G Networks: Methodology, Approach and AI-Mechanisms in SNS JU
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.1 - Environmental, social, and economic drivers and goals for 6G	10.5281/zenodo.16778706	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.1 - Environmental, social, and economic drivers and goals for 6G
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.2 - 6G Use Cases and Requirements	10.5281/zenodo.16779960	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.2 - 6G Use Cases and Requirements
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.3 - Environmental and social view on 6G	10.5281/zenodo.16780232	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.3 - Environmental and social view on 6G
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.4 - 6G Value, Requirements and Ecosystem	10.5281/zenodo.15772634	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D1.4 - 6G Value, Requirements and Ecosystem
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D2.1 - Draft foundation for 6G system design	10.5281/zenodo.16995021	D2.1 Draft foundation for 6G system design
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D2.2 - Foundation of overall 6G system design and preliminary evaluation results	10.5281/zenodo.16995047	Deliverable D2.2 Foundation of overall 6G system design and preliminary evaluation results
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D2.3 - Interim overall 6G system design	10.5281/zenodo.16995059	Deliverable D2.3 Interim overall 6G system design
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D2.4 - End-to-end system evaluation results from the interim overall 6G system	10.5281/zenodo.15796347	Deliverable D2.4 End-to-end system evaluation results from the interim overall 6G system
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D2.5 - Final overall 6G system design	10.5281/zenodo.15796361	Deliverable D2.5 Final overall 6G system design
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D2.6 - Final end-to-end system evaluation results of the overall 6G system design	10.5281/zenodo.15796394	Deliverable D2.6 Final end-to-end system evaluation results of the overall 6G system design
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D3.2 - Initial Architectural enablers	10.5281/zenodo.16995095	Deliverable D3.2 Initial Architectural enablers
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D3.3 - Initial analysis of architectural enablers and framework	10.5281/zenodo.16995133	Deliverable D3.3 Initial analysis of architectural enablers and framework
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D3.5 - Final architectural framework and analysis	10.5281/zenodo.15774984	Deliverable D3.5 Final architectural framework and analysis
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D4.2 - Radio design and spectrum access requirements and key enablers for 6G evolution	10.5281/zenodo.15773276	Radio design and spectrum access requirements and key enablers for 6G evolution (Hexa-X-II Deliverable D4.2)
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D4.3 - Early results of 6G Radio Key Enablers	10.5281/zenodo.15773307	Early results of 6G Radio Key Enablers (Hexa-X-II Deliverable D4.3)
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D4.5 - Final Results of 6G Radio Key Enablers	10.5281/zenodo.15773214	Final Results of 6G Radio Key Enablers (Deliverable D4.5)
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D5.2 - Characteristics and classification of 6G device classes	10.5281/zenodo.16995203	Deliverable D5.2 Characteristics and classification of 6G device classes
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D5.3 - Initial design and validation of technologies and architecture of 6G devices and infrastructure	10.5281/zenodo.16995213	Deliverable D5.3 Initial design and validation of technologies and architecture of 6G devices and infrastructure Hexa-
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D5.5 - Final design of enabling technologies for 6G devices and infrastructure	10.5281/zenodo.15772075	D5.5 – Final design of enabling technologies for 6G devices and infrastructure
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D6.2 - Foundations on 6G Smart Network Management Enablers	10.5281/zenodo.16995220	Deliverable D6.2 Foundations on 6G Smart Network Management Enablers
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D6.3 - Initial Design of 6G Smart Network Management Framework	10.5281/zenodo.16995231	Deliverable D6.3 Initial Design of 6G Smart Network Management Framework
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D6.5 - Final Design on 6G Smart Network Management Framework	10.5281/zenodo.15796540	Deliverable D6.5 Final Design on 6G Smart Network Management Framework
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D7.3 - Dissemination, communication, and clustering	10.5281/zenodo.15773345	D7.3 Dissemination, communication, and clustering (Hexa-X-II)
Deliverable/Report	Hexa-X-II Deliverable D7.6 - Dissemination, communication, and clustering - Final release	10.5281/zenodo.15773231	Hexa-X-II D7.6 Dissemination, communication, and clustering